

MICROFRACTURE PROCESS CHARACTERIZATION OF SHORT GLASS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES BY SCANNING ACOUSTIC MICROSCOPY

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ABSTRACT

Three different fiber surface treatments were made to study these effects on drop-weight impact fracture resistance and static in-plane fracture toughness of injection-molded short glass fiber reinforced nylon 6 plates. Scanning acoustic microscopy (SAM) was used to study the detailed microscopic deformation and fracture process. The SAM observations could reveal some fundamental and quantitative features such as, (1) three-dimensional shape of the crack front, (2) three-dimensional distribution of fibers, (3) matrix plastic deformation and/or matrix microcracking, and (4) fiber/matrix debonding and pull-out. These microscopic deformation and fracture features revealed some of the toughening mechanisms, which were then attempted to be correlated with the macroscopic static and impact fracture properties. The excellent ultrasonic contrast between fibers and matrix could be accomplished by the large acoustic impedance mismatch. Matrix plastic deformation were detected by the enhanced attenuation of the surface waves. Moreover, fiber/matrix debonding and/or matrix microcracking were clearly observed due to the wave reflection at debonded or cracked interfaces.

KEYWORDS: Scanning Acoustic Microscopy; Injection Molding; Glass Fiber; Interface; Low Velocity Impact; Fracture Toughness

1. INTRODUCTION

Injection-molded glass fiber reinforced thermoplastic (GF RTP) composites are being more extensively used as structural materials in aerospace, automobile and sporting goods areas. Such interests have accelerated the recent studies on static strength and toughness properties⁽¹⁾ as well as impact fracture properties.^{(2),(3)} The previous study⁽⁴⁾ has revealed that fracture properties and damage developments of GF RTP are strongly influenced by fiber surface

treatments in both static and impact loading conditions. The detailed micromechanical characteristics, however, should be investigated to understand the fundamental roles of constituent materials including fibers, matrix and fiber/matrix interfaces in the microfracture process. Scanning acoustic microscopy (SAM) has proven to be an excellent technique for such purposes.^{(5),(6)}

In the present study, the SAM observations were performed to characterize the microscopic damage progress near crack tips under tensile loading in injection-molded nylon 6 matrix composites reinforced with randomly-oriented short glass fibers. Toughening mechanisms were then identified through the observed microscopic deformation and fracture features for composites with different fiber surface treatments. These micromechanical characteristics were correlated with the static in-plane fracture toughness and drop-weight impact fracture resistance properties.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Tested Materials Injection-molded glass fiber/nylon 6 plates ($60 \times 60 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$, $V_f = 30\%$) were prepared with three different kinds of fiber surface treatments (Table 1). Surface treatment C was with normal sizing, while surface treatment B was without lubricants, and surface treatment A was without both silane coupling agents and lubricants. The interfacial strength was anticipated to increase in the order of A, B and C. Average fiber length and diameter were $300 \mu\text{m}$ and $13 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. Fibers were mainly oriented parallel to the mold fill direction at surface layers, but normal at central or core regions. Fiber orientation effects were evident as shown in Table 1. The molded specimens were kept at about 20 % humidity until testing.

2.2 Impact Tests Two types of drop-weight impact tests were conducted. The first test was a simple drop-weight test, where a 300-gram weight was fallen from prescribed heights on a cylinder contacted with the specimen plate. The head of the cylinder was of hemispherical shape with 12.7 mm in diameter. The height where 50 % of tested specimens had an initial detected crack (denoted by H_{50}) and the corresponding absorbed energy (E_{50})

TABLE 1 TESTED MATERIALS AND THEIR PROPERTIES

Surface Treatment	Tensile Strength* ¹⁾ (MPa)	$E_{IzOD}^{*2)}$ notched (kJ/m ²)	$E_{IzOD}^{*2)}$ unnotched (kJ/m ²)	$\sigma_B^{*3)}$ L/h=4 (MPa)	$\sigma_B^{*3)}$ L/h=8 (MPa)
A	113.8(L)	5.5	49.5	132(L) 142(T)	113(L) 100(T)
B	163.3(L)	8.4	74.3	224(L) 187(T)	191(L) 149(T)
C	162.6(L)	8.9	81.8	222(L) 209(T)	193(L) 153(T)

*¹⁾ ASTM D638-68, *²⁾ Izod impact value, ASTM D256-56

*³⁾ 3-point bending strength (L: span, h: thickness)

(L): parallel to mold fill direction(MFD), (T): normal to MFD

were calculated. The second test was an instrumented drop-weight test. The impactor-head shape was similar to that of the first test. The impact energy of 65 J (11.7 kg, 3.4 m/s) was well above the perforation energy, and the load and energy-time diagrams were recorded.

2.3 Static Fracture Toughness Tests Static in-plane fracture toughness was measured using compact tension (CT) specimens. Load P and load-line displacement δ were recorded simultaneously with two-channel acoustic emission (AE) signals using a NAIS-AE4000 system. The J -integral approach was used to consider stable crack growth and nonlinear P - δ diagrams. The critical displacement for unstable crack growth initiation, δ_c , was evaluated using AE data to determine the critical J -value, J_c . The experimental details were described in Ref. 4.

2.4 SAM Observations Surface and subsurface images were obtained with a SAM (Olympus UH-3). Input r.f. pulses are supplied to the piezoelectric transducer through a circulator and a matching-box unit, and then a planar longitudinal wave is introduced into a sapphire rod. Water is used as a couplant, and the sapphire/water interface acts as an acoustic lens. The wave is focused on the specimen surface or subsurface. The reflected acoustic wave is then amplified for signal processing to obtain the acoustic image of the specimen, which depends on the elastic modulus, density and viscosity of the specimen.⁽⁶⁾ The 200 or 400 MHz burst signals were used in the present study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Impact Properties Drop-weight impact test results are summarized in Table 2. The E_{50} value increases in the order of materials A, B and C. The initial crack always extends in the mold fill direction just beneath the impact point at the back surface. This is due to fiber orientation effects. Typical dynamic load (energy)-time curves from an instrumented impact test are shown in Fig. 1. The first peak load P_1 [the corresponding absorbed energy E_1] increases in the order of A, B and C. This first peak load corresponds to the crack initiation at the specimen back surface, which was confirmed by high-speed photographs. The ratio of E_{50} for materials A, B and C is different from that for E_1 probably due to different applied impact energies and fracture processes. The second peak load P_2 is, on the other hand, larger for material B than for material C. The P_2 value is smaller than the P_1 for both materials B

TABLE 2 SUMMARY OF IMPACT TEST RESULTS

Mat'l	E_{50} (J)	P_1 (kN)	E_1 (J)	P_2 (kN)	E_t (J)
A	0.65[0.69]*	1.29[0.56]	0.62[0.27]	1.66[0.91]	5.57[0.68]
B	0.82[0.87]	2.10[0.91]	1.85[0.80]	1.95[1.07]	7.49[0.92]
C	0.94	2.29	2.31	1.82	8.14

E_{50} : fracture energy where 50% of specimens are cracked,

P_1 : 1st peak load, E_1 : absorbed energy at P_1 ,

P_2 : 2nd peak load, E_t : total absorbed energy

* number in [] is the ratio of each value to that of material C.

FIGURE 1. Dynamic load [absorbed energy]-time diagrams

and C, but larger for material A. The P_2 value for material A is, however, smaller than those for materials B and C. The total absorbed energy E_1 value also increases in the order of A, B and C. In summary, material A has low interfacial strength, which results in the lower impact resistance. Material C has a higher P_1 or E_1 value than material B, which means C is better than B and A, if the crack initiation is a design criterion of these materials.

3.2 Static Fracture Toughness

Typical $P-\delta$ diagrams with cumulative AE energies are shown in Fig. 2. The J -integral approach is necessary to consider stable crack growth and nonlinear $P-\delta$ diagrams. Figure 3 shows specimen photos after some crack propagation. The damage region at the crack tip is wider for material A than those for materials B and C. The $J-\delta$ diagrams can be obtained from the above $P-\delta$ curves, using Landes and Begley's method⁽⁷⁾ or Merkle and Corten's method.⁽⁸⁾ The difference of both methods is negligible in the present specimens. The critical displacement for unstable crack growth, δ_c , on the other hand, can be determined by the point where the increasing rate of the cumulative AE energy becomes large, as shown in Fig. 2. Then, the critical J -value, J_c , can be calculated as a J -

FIGURE 2. $P-\delta$ diagrams and cumulative AE energy

(a) material A (b) material B (c) material C

FIGURE 3. Photos after crack growth**TABLE 3** J_c VALUES

Material	δ_c (mm)	J_c (kJ/m ²)
A	1.37	6.0[0.83]*
B	1.34	7.3[0.91]
C	1.34	8.0

* number in [] is the ratio of each value to that of material C.

value corresponding to the δ_c value in the J - δ diagrams. Table 3 summarizes both δ_c and the corresponding J_c values. The J_c increases in the order of A, B and C, which agrees well with the tendency in the E_{50} value in Table 2. Thus, static fracture toughness properties are closely related with impact properties in the present GF RTP specimens, which indicates that one property can be predicted by the other property.

3.3 SEM Surface Observations Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of fracture surfaces after static in-plane fracture toughness tests are shown in Fig. 4. Material A has lower interfacial strength, and interfacial debonding is easy to occur, which results in the crack bifurcation. The fiber pull-out length is relatively large (100 μ m on the average), and resin holes left after fiber pull-outs can be found easily. Almost no resin is found on fiber surfaces. For material B, on the other hand, the average pull-out length is 60 μ m, and the resin plastic deformation tends to hide resin holes after pull-outs. Some remaining resin can be found on fiber surfaces. This tendency becomes more evident for material C, where the average pull-out length is 40 μ m, and resin plastic deformation becomes clear due to high fiber/resin interfacial strength.

(a) material A

(b) material B

(c) material C

FIGURE 4. SEM photos of fracture surfaces after static in-plane fracture toughness tests

3.4 SAM Surface and Subsurface Observations Some of the characteristic SAM photos are shown in Figs. 5-7. In general, black and white contrast in acoustic images of the GF RTP specimens is determined from the following acoustic factors:

- Difference in reflection indexes of fibers and resin,
- Surface curvatures,

- (c) Difference in surface wave speeds, and
 (d) Difference in attenuation coefficients.

Since the observed specimen surfaces are almost flat, the factor (b) can be neglected in the present study. Factors (a), (c) and (d) are discussed in the following.

FIGURE 5. SAM photos indicating fiber/resin debonding (impact)

FIGURE 6. SAM photos indicating plastic deformation near the crack tip (static)

Difference in reflection indexes of fibers and resin corresponds to the difference in acoustic impedances Z of constituent materials. The reflection ratio R is calculated from the following equation: $R = (Z_1 - Z_2)^2 / (Z_1 + Z_2)^2$, where subscripts 1 and 2 denote fibers and resin, respectively. Fibers and resin can be clearly distinguished in SAM photos because of the large acoustic impedance mismatch between fibers and resin. The contrast between fibers and resin is much higher in SAM photos than in optical micrographs. Moreover, SAM reveals various features on flat specimen surfaces, which cannot be clearly observed by SEM. Large acoustic impedance mismatch is expected for fiber/resin debonding, where the brightness at the debonded region becomes large. Such fiber/resin debonding can be observed in Fig. 5.

FIGURE 7. SAM photo indicating remaining plastic deformation along crack path

FIGURE 8. Comparison of SAM photos for materials A, B and C (static)

FIGURE 9. Comparison of SAM photos for materials A, B and C (impact)

Let us consider the acoustic contrast appearing at crack-tip regions after static fracture toughness tests, as shown in Fig. 6. First, the contrast between fibers and resin is evident when the focus is on the specimen surface (focal depth $z = 0 \mu\text{m}$). The subsurface image ($z = -20 \mu\text{m}$) gives some white region, which cannot be observed in the surface image. Such white region tends to disappear if the focal depth is deeper ($z = -25 \mu\text{m}$). The above white region is believed to correspond to the highly plastically-deformed region, which appears due to the difference in surface wave speeds.

Surface SAM images in Fig. 7 shows clear acoustic contrast along the crack path. Acoustic impedance mismatch is small between water and the present specimen itself, and the reflection ratio is small at the specimen surface. Attenuation of surface waves was measured to be 3-9 dB close to the crack path. This high attenuation along the crack path gives strong contrast even in surface images.

Comparison between materials A, B and C is shown in Fig. 8 for static loading, and in Fig. 9 for impact loading. For material A, extensive fiber/resin debondings occur frequently near the main crack, and the main crack advances with the coalescence of debondings and the main crack. For materials B and C, on the other hand, several microcracks appear at resin regions near the main crack-tip, and the main crack is connected with these microcracks. Thus, interfacial properties change the crack growth characteristics. These microscopic deformation and fracture features are well correlated with the macroscopic static and impact fracture properties obtained in Sections 3.1 and 3.2.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Three different fiber surface treatments were made to study these effects on drop-weight impact fracture resistance and static in-plane fracture toughness of injection-molded short glass fiber reinforced nylon 6 plates. Scanning acoustic microscopy was used to study the detailed microscopic deformation and fracture process. The SAM observations revealed some fundamental and quantitative features such as,

- (1) three-dimensional shape of the crack front,
- (2) three-dimensional distribution of fibers and their effects on damage progress,
- (3) matrix plastic deformation and/or matrix microcracking, and
- (4) fiber/matrix debonding and pull-out.

These microscopic deformation and fracture features revealed some of the toughening mechanisms, which were then attempted to be correlated with the macroscopic fracture properties. The excellent contrast between fibers and matrix could be accomplished by the large acoustic impedance mismatch. Matrix plastic deformation were detected by the enhanced attenuation of the surface waves. Moreover, fiber/matrix debonding and/or matrix microcracking were clearly observed due to the wave reflection at debonded or cracked interfaces.

In-situ SAM observation technique is now under development to obtain dynamic deformation and fracture process of GFRTCP CT-specimens. These efforts are believed to help the understanding of micromechanical explanation of GFRTCP fractures.

5. REFERENCES

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